

GUIDEBOOK

Virtual Innovation Competition

VIC2024

"AI Leading the Charge"

Start Now

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<https://registro.myvic.asia>

[doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10153679](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10153679)

Strategic Partners

Universiti Teknologi MARA Startup Company

Cawangan Kelantan

Strategic Partnerships

CAMARINES SUR
POLYTECHNIC COLLEGES
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asia
RESEARCH NEWS

WORLD ALERTS
WORLD CONFERENCE ALERTS

ALL CONFERENCE ALERT
ACADEMIC CONFERENCES AT A GLANCE

The Union of Arab Academics

IYSA
Indonesian Young Scientist Association

Laman Teknologi

What is Virtual Innovation Competition?

Virtual Innovation Competition is organized by DIGIT360 and Digital Information Interest Group (DIGIT), in collaboration with Information Science Studies, College of Computing, Informatics and Mathematic, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Kelantan Branch, Malaysia; Universitas Ngudi Waluyo, Indonesia; Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges, Philippines; Asia Research News; Indian Innovators Association, India; The Union Of Arab Academics, Yemen; Indonesian Young Scientist Association, Indonesia; Nusantara Training and Research, Indonesia; Academica Press Solutions; RR Texnology and Laman Teknologi.

VIC2024
Online innovation event
featuring diverse projects.

VIC History

2020
347

PEOPLE JOIN

2021
672

PEOPLE JOIN

2022
872

PEOPLE JOIN

2023
1012

PEOPLE JOIN

2024 FORECAST
1200+

PEOPLE JOIN

Virtual Innovation Competition

CATEGORY	E-CERTIFICATE	MEDAL	REGISTRATION FEE *	EXTRA MEDAL *
Professional	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award		RM 150 (Local) USD100 (Int)	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)
Tertiary (Social Science)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award		RM 100 (Local) USD 50 (Int)	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)
Tertiary (Science & Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award		RM 100 (Local) USD 50 (Int)	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)
Virtual 3-Minute Thesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award		RM 100 (Local) USD 50 (Int)	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)
Young Scientist (Secondary School)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award	No Medal Provided	FREE	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)
Junior Scientist (Primary School)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation• Award• Special Award	No Medal Provided	FREE	RM 50 (Local) USD 50 (Int)

Professional Category

Open to Academician (Teacher, Lecturer, Academic Consultant, etc.), Practitioners, and Industries.

7 Clusters: Industrial Technology, Energy & Environment, Health & Wellness, Cyber Technology, Logistics & Transportation, Social Creativity & Innovation, and Special Needs innovation.

Awards:

- *Academique D'Or*
- *The Best*
- *Medal (Gold, Silver, and Bronze)*
- *e-certificate*

Professional

RM 150 Local (Malaysia)

USD 100 (International)

Tertiary Category

Open to Students at higher education (certificate to PhD)

2 Clusters: Science & Technology (ST), and Social Science (SS)

Awards:

- *Diamond Award*
- *Medal (Gold, Silver, and Bronze)*
- *e-certificate*

Tertiary

RM 100 Local (Malaysia)

USD 50 (International)

3-Minute Thesis Category

Open to Students at higher education (certificate to PhD)

Awards:

- *Diamond Scholar Award*
- *Medal (Gold, Silver, and Bronze)*
- *e-certificate*

3-Minute Thesis (3MT)

RM 100 Local (Malaysia)

USD 50 (International)

Young Scientist Category

Open to Secondary Schools Students (12 years to 17 years) from Malaysia and international students. **School Authorization Letter is MANDATORY.**

Awards:

- *Diamond Award*
- *No Medal provided*
- *e-certificate*

Young Scientist (YS)

FREE (No FEE) – PAJSK Provided
e-certificate provided. Medal can be purchased at
the end of the event.

Junior Scientist Category

Open to Primary Schools Students (7 years to 11 years) from Malaysia and international students. **School Authorization Letter is MANDATORY.**

Awards:

- *Diamond Award*
- *No Medal provided*
- *e-certificate*

Junior Scientist (JS)

FREE (No FEE) – PAJSK Provided
e-certificate provided. Medal can be purchased at
the end of the event.

School Authorization Letter

- 01 **Download School Authorization Letter Template**
[Bahasa Melayu](#) | [English Version](#)
- 02 Please attached the letter with the school's official letterhead and obtain the signature as well as the official stamp.
- 03 Upload the document/letter to Google Drive – set permission to 'anyone can view'.
- 04 Copy the Google Drive URL and paste it together when submitting the Video.

REMINDER!

**IT IS MANDATORY TO SUBMIT THE 'SCHOOL
AUTHORIZATION LETTER' FOR THE YOUNG SCIENTIST
AND JUNIOR SCIENTIST CATEGORY**

THANK YOU

VIC | How to Register

Project Registration Process

A step-by-step guide

SCHOOL AUTHORIZATION LETTER IS MANDATORY FOR PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS!

Register using Registro Portal

<https://registro.myvic.asia>

Receive an automatic Letter of Acceptance through Registro Portal

Prepare presentation video and evidence (optional)

Upload video to YouTube and Get the Video ID:

Example:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gaxy2dyhMgA>

Copy the last ID only (i.e. gaxy2dyhMgA)

Complete payment through the Registro Portal

Update Video Detail (YouTube Video ID) and/or evidence link (Preferably Google Drive)

Virtual Booth URL will be provided

User is informed about their result

1. Register your project at Registro Portal: <https://registro.myvic.asia>
2. A letter of Acceptance (LOA) will be automatically issued for the accepted project. Please check Registro Portal for the copy of the **PROJECT ID (I.E. YS10, 3MT1, SS1, ST1)**
3. Upload your video to your YouTube account. **Please ensure that you set the permission to public or unlisted.**
4. Pay the participation fee via Registro Payment System (for categories with Fee).
5. Upload your video link, and evidence (optional – preferably Google Drive) via Registro Portal.
6. **For Young Scientists and Junior Scientists category, you are required to attach an approval letter from the school.**
7. **The letter can be downloaded here: [Bahasa Melayu](#) | [English Version](#)**
8. **Please attached the letter with the school's official letterhead and obtain the signature as well as the official stamp.**
9. **Then, upload the document/letter to Google Drive – set permission to 'anyone can view'.**
10. The organizer will verify the payment, video, and/or evidence link.
11. Once verified, the video will be uploaded to **VIC Virtual Booth**.
12. A panel of expert reviewers will review all the projects submitted.
13. **Most Outstanding Video Awards will be selected by the juries.**
14. Announcement of results through the VIC YouTube Channel, VIC website, and email.
15. **The judges' decision is final, and no appeals will be entertained.**

Video Content – General (Excluding 3MT)

Video Duration: Within 6 Minutes and 30 Seconds

Orientation: Landscape

Submission: Upload to your own YouTube Channel. Please set permission to 'Unlisted' or 'Public'.

Rules

1. Must start with video introduction of team members – including name, and organization/university name.
2. Contents – Introduction, problem statement, solution, impacts, commercialization potential, publication (if available), copyright (if available), any additional criteria.

Video Content – 3-Minute-Thesis

Video Duration: Within 3 Minutes and 30 Seconds

Orientation: Landscape

Submission: Upload to your own YouTube Channel. Please set permission to 'Unlisted' or 'Public'.

Rules

1. Must start with video introduction of team members – including name, and organization/university name.
2. Contents – Introduction, problem statement, methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusion.
3. Additional criteria - Impacts, commercialization potential, publication (if available), copyright (if available), etc.
4. The Presentation must be in a spoken word only (no poem, singing, voice replacement, etc.).
5. The presentation must be in English.

VIC Awards

VIC

Grand Award

3

RD

ACADÉMIQUE

D'OR

VIRTUAL INNOVATION COMPETITION

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USD 20
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Malaysia Journal of Invention and Innovation (eISSN: 2976-2170) an international journal that provides leading edge research and findings focussing on theories, methods, invention, innovation, and applications in all fields especially in Social Sciences, Science and Technology, Informatics, Science, and related field of study. Malaysia Journal of Invention and Innovation (MJII) is indexed by:

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- CiteFactor
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- Google Scholar
- Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE)
- COSMOS Impact Factor

1. Download the Extended Abstract Template: [[Download](#)]
2. Prepare your paper based on the Template provided.
3. Pay the publication Fee (refer to Table below) [[Online Payment](#)]
4. Submit your Extended Abstract to the following URL: <https://academicpress.digit360.com.my/apsp/index.php/publish/>
5. The submission deadline is 31st May 2024.

Category	Fee
Professional	~FREE~
Tertiary (Social Science)	~FREE~
Tertiary (Science & Technology)	FREE
3-Minute-Thesis	FREE
Young Scientist	RM 50
Junior Scientist	RM 50

A red starburst graphic with a yellow outline, containing the text "OPTIONAL – NOT MANDATORY".

OPTIONAL –
NOT
MANDATORY

By submitting to VIC, I agreed that:

1. My information will be collected under the Personal Data Protection Act 2010 (PDPA).
2. The organiser may contact me for further communication regarding the event that i am a participant.
3. My registration is consider completed once i pay the registration fee (if applicable) and submitted the presentation video.
4. No refund is available once I have submitted the complete registration.
- 5. The judges' decision is final, and no appeals will be entertained.**
6. It is NOT ADVISEABLE to enter this competition if you have already won at other events - especially international event as we cannot promise that you will be getting the same result here.
7. The organiser hold no legal responsibility on any claim by participants - please read the term and conditions accordingly.

General Rules and Regulation

1. **VIC is open to all participant from primary schools to professionals.**
2. **The participation fee is only applicable for all categories EXCEPT primary and secondary schools.**
3. **Participation in primary (Junior Scientist) and secondary schools (Young Scientist) is FREE. However, the organizer only provided an e-certificate of participation and award.**
4. **School Authorization Letter is mandatory for primary and secondary schools.**
5. **Extra medal for Primary and Secondary schools is available for purchase with a fee of RM50 (local) and USD50 (International) per medal.**
6. **The extra medal price is inclusive of delivery and packaging FEE.**
7. **For other PAID category, ONE MEDAL is provided for FREE. Extra medal is also available for purchase with a fee of RM50 (local) and USD50 (International) per medal (inclusive of delivery and packaging FEE.).**
8. **The organizer only provided ONE e-certificate that included all the participant's name. However, a customized e-certificate that contain each individual participant can be purchased later with a fee of RM15 per e-certificate/individual.**
9. **All payment is NON-REFUNDABLE. Failure to complete your registration before the end of submission will VOID your participation.**

General Rules and Regulation

- 1. Junior Scientist (JS) is applicable for primary school's students. The project MUST BE LED by a primary school student. Teacher or supervisor may insert their name as a member. Failure to comply may lead to disqualification of participation.**
- 2. Young Scientist (YS) is applicable for secondary school's students. The project MUST BE LED by a secondary school student. Teacher or supervisor may insert their name as a member. Failure to comply may lead to disqualification of participation.**
- 3. Tertiary Social Science or Tertiary Science and Technology is applicable for the STUDENTS of higher learning institution. The project MUST BE LED by a STUDENT. Teacher/Lecturer/Supervisor may insert their name as a member. Failure to comply may lead to disqualification of participation.**
- 4. Presentation video must not exceed 6 minutes 30 seconds.**
- 5. The use of third-party-software to boost video view and likes is strictly prohibited. Failure to comply may lead to disqualification of participation.**
- 6. All decisions are FINAL. No request or appeal will be entertained.**
- 7. The data collected for the registration process is strictly confidential and will not be shared to other entity.**

General Rules and Regulation

- 8. However, the organizer may use the information for further communication with the participants such as to update the progress of the event and participation in future event.**
- 9. All presentation video must start with each member introducing themselves via Recorded Video – to ensure originality and consent of all members and advisor (s).**
- 10. The innovation and/or invention must be original – the organizer will disqualify any innovation and/or invention that did not fulfil the given criteria**

VIC Premium Medal

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USD 50
ONLY!**

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VIC24 | Young Scientist
🔥 CR: 0.1379 | 👍 4 Likes | 👁 29 Views | 🗑 25 times | ★ LS: 29.6
Like it? | Support them now!
Report Plagiarism

Evidence (Google Drive URL - Optional)

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17bnNuA0diyozxBHz1MdM-9714bjyf8Q1?usp=sharing>

Warning - You cannot submit until you make correction to the registration details!

- Please check your registration. For Young Scientist, Junior Scientist, and Tertiary, the first name must be a student (Status=STUDENT).
- You may click 'edit details' from the dashboard and make the necessary correction.

Integrity is priceless! If you received this message, please ensure that the first name on the registration list is an active student. Please select STATUS=STUDENT.

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For Your Attention

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See You Next

